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Entrepreneurial Well-Being Genetic Components Vs Social-Family Elements in a Family Network

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to highlight that, even if there could be genetic components in being an entrepreneur, social and cognitive elements can positively favour and accelerate entrepreneurial psychological well-being. Through a theoretical approach the social and cognitive elements emerge as fundamental nodes of entrepreneurial well-being. Starting from the consideration that personal well-being determines a positive mood that activates some brain's areas; this positive emotion circulates more rapidly in a family network because here are indissoluble bonds that no other group presents.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial well-being, Genetic components*

Introduction

Entrepreneurial behaviour seems to emerge through social links (networks and family) that help to reach a good level of well-being. All the social aspects of a person (social status, environment, family, gender) have a strong influence in forming an entrepreneur. Perhaps there is a genetic predisposition to being an entrepreneur, but the socio-emotional context could influence his formation.

Measuring the psychological reactions of consumers is easier (pupillary size-response, vascular activity, facial muscle activity) than establishing the psychological and neurological connections of being an (happy) entrepreneur. Neuroscience is a science that can explain the composition of the human brain and its reaction to different external stimuli. It has cold cognition useful for a rational analysis.

The aim of this work is to theoretically demonstrate, through a cognitive analysis, that the atmosphere in a family firm psychologically influences the attitude and managing to entrepreneurship, so that psycho-emotional well-being deeply affects entrepreneurial results.

Entrepreneurs' well-being and individual happiness.

Emotions and problems belong both to a person and so to an entrepreneur, as they are normal life situations. What makes the difference is how the man-entrepreneur manages them and how the attitude determines the status of well-being (Huppert, 2009), but researchs also includes biological studies. The common element both in a family network of firms and in a simple network of firms is the entrepreneurial presence.

Is there a genetic component in the process of becoming an entrepreneur?

H1: An entrepreneur's happiness and well-being are founded on social links and the differences in gender could strongly affect this.

Brain

One of the main problems in selecting candidates to study the links between genes and entrepreneurship is the *a priori* identification of variables: researchers have not found the characteristics of being an entrepreneur, but they usually select what they think are the characteristics. Genetics show that it is necessary to study a very big sample of individuals in order to identify a “universal law”. Guiso and Rustichini (2011) show that entrepreneurs with a lower digit ratio and a greater exposure to prenatal testosterone have more employees. Johnson (2009), Nicolaou and Shane (2009) and Lindquist et al. (2012) worked on biology and gene and genome. Several quantitative studies on this argument found some genetic components that highlight both the attitude to starting a new business (Nicolaou et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2009; Thurik, 2015), and the tendency to identify new entrepreneurial opportunity (Nicolaou et al. 2009). However, Quaye et al. (2012) didn't find a gene that arrives at genoma-wide meaningful level and that is strictly linked with entrepreneurial elements. Zald et al. (2009) show that there are also several studies on dopamine receptors in the cerebral cortex of entrepreneurs. On investigating the relation between a single nucleotide polymorphism in the DRD3 (dopamine receptor D3) and the inclination to be an entrepreneur in a sample of 1,335 British subjects Nicolaou (2011) found a link between a specific gene and entrepreneurship. Unfortunately, other experiments on Nicolaou's data are not possible and, moreover, Nicolaou's work has been much criticized.

Social elements are also strictly correlated with the brain: in the post-natal stage the brain undergoes major changes in the period from 2 years until puberty after which, in adulthood, the frontal lobes that determine emotional control develop.

Psychological elements

From a psychological point of view, functioning effectively, means realizing positive goals and positive relationships resulting in mental well-being. Many experimental studies (Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005; Gasper and Clore, 2000) shown that a favourable and positive mood stimulates other cognitive processes. Positive facts and emotions are both the cause and the effect of the cognitive and behavioural processes. A deficiency in serotonergic function could produce a low level or the absence of a positive mood (Flory et al., 2004).

Personality and genetics

An interesting feature is the connection between personality and genetic elements in the entrepreneurial game. Extroversion is a personality mediator useful helping to explain the mechanisms through which genetics and environmental factors impact entrepreneurship. Neuroticism also plays a fundamental role in the entrepreneurial gender-personality-genetic equation.

Deaton (2008) used the Gallup World Poll and Gallup-Healthways index as indicators of well-being. However, they are insufficient since well-being and happiness are multidimensional.

H2: Other social context's variables must be considered: the familial environment.

Social entrepreneurship could improve the behavioural health problems of entrepreneurs, as well as community, economic, and social development. Glaeser (2011) identifies quality of life as one of the main elements that influence the place where we work and live. Consequently, if a place is good to live and work in, the inhabitants would perceive happiness and a sense of well-being. Happiness is measured by several indicators, as is the concept of well-being. The happiness of an entrepreneur could contribute to improving the well-being of others and of the environment.

In the link of happiness -entrepreneurs, the role of the Easterlin-Paradox that high levels of income are not associated with happiness, is recognized (Easterlin, 1974).

Well-being in a family firm and network

The emotional context in which a person lives and operates and his cognitive processes are important (Chrisman ety al., 2012; Kotlar and De Massis, 2013). Functioning well (sense of purpose, experiencing positive links) and feeling good (interest, affection, happiness) are crucial. Therefore, the way of managing negative emotions is very important for psychological and mental well-being. The emotional process is situated in the prefrontal cortex and responds to negative and positive emotions in different ways. The use of FMRI and EEG show that if a person has positive emotions the left part of the prefrontal area is more reactive than the right. On the contrary, negative sensations are detected in the right area. The

anthropological constitution of the mind could scientifically explain many things. However, other mechanisms also explain well-being.

Thus, there is a basis for H1 and H2.

Ryff's scale (1989) of psychological well-being is frequently used to measure the positive level-mood of a personality. Usually, a high level of education presents a higher tendency to depression, especially for men, compared to those with a low level of education (Chevalier and Feinstein, 2006). But, gender in entrepreneurial and familial life must be taken into consideration. Jennings and Brush (2013) and Yadav and Unni (2016) demonstrated that when entrepreneurship is a family activity, then women are also valid entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial happiness has to be analysed in an environmental context, i.e. the family, network and external relations. These contexts influence the socio-cognitive elements of each entrepreneur which, in addition to each one's own internal and codified information, triggers some specific areas of the brain.

Genetic components of being an entrepreneur with the familial- networking elements close the circuit of influence for well-being.

FIG. 1: A theoretical model

Source: own interpretation

H3: The socio-emotional elements that influence well-being are stronger in a familial network of entrepreneurs than in a single unit.

Relations among agents play a strategic role in network formation. Nodes usually determine the structure of a network, so in a situation where the choice of linking two nodes stems from one side only, this results in a non-cooperative approach.

The resource-based theory (Barney, 1986; Alvarez, 2003) underlines the strategies and tacit social aspects as the factors that influence the competitive advantages of both the firm-entrepreneurs and the group. Therefore, beyond the division of labour and agglomeration economies, the social and knowledge spillovers that a network produces must be considered. Each firm of the network is a storage of skills and each entrepreneur in the group uses this information to gain non-mutual benefit. All these aspects are present in a family-network and it has high barriers: only members of a family of the net can be members of the group.

Family firm and network

What is the strength of a good family-network? The elements previously identified are purely rational and "soulless". However, the family has many magnetic and spiritual facets (Nicholson, 2008; Zellwegwer et al., 2012; Linton et al., 2016) that influence well-being.

In network theory the relation entrepreneurs - network presents the structure-governance-content aspects. The presence of a good entrepreneurial team, with a family leader, could be a key competitive element. It is commonly believed that being an entrepreneur is the result of a genetic attitude (i.e. nature-hypothesis), or

strong abilities and experiences (i.e. nurture- hypothesis) (Holt et al., 2018; White et al., 2007). Many, but not all family entrepreneurs have both elements and it could be interpreted as the probability of becoming a family-inherited-entrepreneur. The emotional element is very strong within the family and could condition the family group (social-identity theory). Personal identity and corporate identity overlap and self-destruct. The family firm is an extension of the family (Klotz and Neubaum, 2016). The latter always prefers to protect the internal atmosphere between the members-workers of the firm. Thus, H3 has a foundation.

The social ingredients of family-entrepreneurs are the threads for the families and the network. Those factors are the tight mesh of the group and are also the strong barriers. In a family-network, the network specific relations and characteristics are amplified. In a family-network firms are closely connected because of the specific and peculiar social elements of each single family that give it its distinctive sign (know-how, social perspective, personal way of behaving).

The genetic component of familiarity, the “family air” of an entrepreneur and the social factors of the family are present.

H4: In a family network there are high emotional-historical enter barriers that define the type of entrepreneur.

The networking knowledge of families is usually codified. It has a socio-historical basis and is spread through relations between family-members. So, both the social capital of the single unit of the family-network favour the acceleration of knowledge and other mechanisms in the network. Therefore, the higher the level of these elements in each single unit, the higher the transfer of new knowledge among the firms of the group (Sanchez-Famoso et al., 2015). The interaction among entrepreneurs in a family firm network is easier than in a network. The strong historical influence can exalt all the positive features of the entrepreneurial tradition and it could produce an erroneous psychological belief that the way of entrepreneurially-acting is the best choice. Thus, there could be a gap in the psychological net. At the exact moment in which the socio-emotional aspects regress, there is a weakness in the network and in its well-being. The ability of the family-network is to fill this gap with trust through non-redundant information, thus reinforcing the reputational network (Gurrieri, 2013).

If the socio-emotional aspect does not work, there is no longer a family-network of entrepreneurs. H4 has a foundation.

The entrepreneurs involved in a family-network present a strong identity and an entrepreneurial culture that are more evident if the level of generational involvement is high.

Fig. 2: Family firms Network-Well-being

Source: own interpretation

Within familial- network the well-being of relatives exchanged through the well-being and personality of the members, entrepreneurs and non-members of the group.

Social entrepreneurship develops strategies supporting social change to improve the well-being of people in society. A social entrepreneur must have a deep knowledge of social problems and innovations depend on actors' inclusion.

While assuming that there is a genetic component in being an entrepreneur, there is no doubt that the well-being and the positive mood of the individual influence their activities and those of the entire family.

Conclusion

The emotional and social aspects are linked to the personal characteristics of entrepreneurs and families, and, if it were possible to use genetic factors, we could have a wider vision of each family and of the family network.

This work is an attempt to highlight what determines entrepreneurial well-being and its importance. Starting from the consideration that personal happiness determines a positive mood that activates some areas of our brain, this optimistic emotion circulates more rapidly in a family-network.

One limit of the paper is the absence of data for supporting the theoretical model. Further research must go in this direction

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